

Ensuring equity in the integration of artificial intelligence in engineering biology

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AI in engineering biology

Engineering biology: '[...] the design, scaling and commercialisation of biology-derived products and services that can transform sectors or produce existing products more sustainably' [1]

AI bias can emerge at all stages of the development pipeline

- Data collection → Algorithm design → Implementation

Systematic literature review

Timespan: 2015-2024

Databases: Scopus/Web of Science

("artificial intelligence" OR ai) AND (medic* OR health OR healthcare) AND (equit* OR inequit* OR equalit* OR inequalit* OR inclusi* OR bias* OR fair* OR unfair* OR disparit* OR justice* OR injustice* OR divers*)

Articles by year

Articles by medical field

Stakeholder interviews

Open-ended interviews to be conducted with stakeholders along the AI development pipeline

Nine interviews conducted so far:

- Scientists (n=6)
- AI developers (n=1)
- Healthcare practitioners (n=1)
- Industry actors (n=1)

Findings from stakeholder interviews

Themes	Quotes
AI use widespread for routine tasks	<i>'Now I use a coding copilot [...] and it saves me minutes to hours looking up stuff that I would eventually figure out [...] and I get back to the job I actually like doing'</i>
AI being used to conduct research	<i>'The only hope on the horizon is AI [in controlling cancer]'</i>
Bias and inaccuracies a key issue	<i>'The moment you give a direction to your AI [...] you bias it to some extent'</i>

Findings from stakeholder interviews

Themes	Quotes
AI just another tool	<i>'With any technology, like there's positives and negatives'</i>
Human expertise still important	<i>'I'm a firm believer that [...] an AI tool shouldn't replace a human [...] the human still needs to bear the ultimate responsibility to make the final decision'</i>
Lack of guidelines around AI use	<i>'I think it's the wild west at the moment with regards to that [guidelines]'</i>